

Modelling Energy Demand from Air Conditioning in Households Using MAED: Suriname Case Study

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ABOUT EMP-LAC

The Energy Modelling Platform for Latin America and the Caribbean (EMP-LAC) is an important event organized by the OpTIMUS community. This free initiative provides participants with access to expert trainers, interactive discussion forums, and personalized coaching on how to use models and tools for energy planning and analysis. Notably, all of the models and tools presented are free and open source, promoting inclusivity and collaboration in the energy sector. Participants benefit not only from the event, but also from the ability to engage with courses at their own pace, thanks to the availability of resources on the OpenLearn platform. This comprehensive approach not only encourages knowledge exchange but also empowers individuals to improve their energy modelling skills, fostering a community committed to sustainable energy practices in the region.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report performs a bottom-up demand-side analysis using the Model for Analysis of Energy Demand (MAED) to simulate the annual energy demand from air conditioning in households in Suriname's urban districts of Paramaribo and Wanica between 2019 and 2033. Three different growth rates are used to calculate potential future percentages of air-conditioned households. These percentages are then used in MAED to simulate three different baseline scenario types, followed by an efficient cooling scenario and an IEA scenario for each baseline scenario type to analyze energy demand and determine which scenarios result in the greatest energy savings. The results show that the IEA Scenario saves more energy for each baseline scenario type than the Efficient Cooling Scenario, with average annual savings of 0.000526 GW (4,607,760 kWh) or more between 2025 and 2029, and 0.000797 GW (6,981,720 kWh) or more between 2030 and 2033. The IEA Scenario requires households to replace their existing air conditioners with more efficient air conditioners every five years; however, given Suriname's economic situation, it is unclear whether this scenario will be financially feasible for residential customers; thus, economic analysis for this scenario should be conducted in the future.

INTRODUCTION

In 2018, approximately 33.7% of households in Suriname had installed and operational air conditioners. Climate control systems account for approximately 40% of a building's energy consumption [1]. Given that climate control accounts for a significant portion of total energy consumption, a bottom-up demand-side analysis is performed using the Model for Analysis of Energy Demand (MAED) to simulate the annual energy demand from air conditioning in households in Suriname's urban districts of Paramaribo and Wanica in 2019 through 2033. The districts of Paramaribo and Wanica were chosen for the analysis because they account for around 66% of Suriname's households and have detailed data on the number of households in each district in the environmental statistics reports [2] [3]. This report aims to demonstrate MAED's capabilities by simulating three scenarios with varying coefficients of performance (COP) for air conditioners. There are no energy efficiency policy standards for cooling appliances in Suriname at the time of writing this report, thus the simulated scenarios have the benefit of providing policymakers an example of how the final energy demand for air conditioning in the household sector changes once energy efficiency standards for cooling appliances are implemented, as well as how much energy can be saved in the process.

METHODOLOGY

The MAED model is a simulation tool used to predict future energy demands based on socioeconomic, technological, and demographic factors. It consists of two modules, MAED D and MAED EL, which calculate total energy and hourly electric load respectively [4]. In this study, the model was used to estimate air conditioning energy demand in households in Suriname's districts Paramaribo and Wanica from 2019 to 2033.

The most recent data on Suriname's percentage of households with installed and operational air conditioners is from 2018. As a result, three different growth rates were used in MAED to estimate potential future percentages of air-conditioned households. A low percentage growth, an average (mid) percentage growth and a high percentage growth of 0.2%, 0.5%, and 0.7% per year, respectively. These percentages are then used in MAED to simulate three different scenarios, analyse energy demand and determine which scenarios produce the best results in terms of energy savings.

The scenarios discussed are the baseline scenario, the efficient cooling scenario, and the IEA scenario.

- In the Baseline Scenario, an average household's air conditioner is assumed to have a COP of 3.52 from 2019 to 2033. In this scenario no new air conditioners with higher efficiency are introduced.
- In the Efficient Cooling Scenario, air conditioners with higher efficiency are used. This scenario simulates the energy demand for air conditioning in households when COP 3.52 air conditioners are replaced with COP 4.0 air conditioners beginning in 2025.
- In the IEA scenario, air conditioners with a COP of 3.52 are first replaced by air conditioners with a COP of 4.8 in 2025, followed by air conditioners with a COP of 5.5 in 2030. This scenario is based on the IEA's estimation for the average efficiency of new air conditioners in the Net Zero Scenario [5].

RESULTS

MAED uses the previously mentioned growth rates to estimate potential future percentages of air-conditioned households in Suriname's districts Paramaribo and Wanica, resulting in three types of baseline scenarios. The baseline scenario types mentioned are Baseline Low, Baseline Middle, and Baseline High.

CHART TABLE

Figure 1 Final Energy Demand of Air Conditioning Baseline Mid

MAED allows you to view the results of each simulation as a chart or table. Figure 1 depicts a chart of the final energy demand of air conditioning for the Baseline Middle scenario type. The results for each baseline scenario type are then exported to Excel and plotted in a single chart, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Final Energy Demand for Air Conditioning for Baseline Scenario Types

The Efficient Cooling Scenario and the IEA Scenario are then simulated in MAED for each baseline scenario type and exported to Excel. Figure 3 shows a comparison of the final energy demand of the baseline scenario types to the Efficient Cooling Scenario and the IEA Scenario.

Figure 3 Final Energy Demand for Air Condition Comparison

The final energy demands of the Efficient Cooling Scenario and the IEA Scenario are then subtracted from the final energy demands of Baseline Low, Baseline Mid, and Baseline High to calculate potential energy savings between 2025 and 2033. Figure 4 illustrates the energy savings for the aforementioned scenarios in a single chart.

Figure 4 Energy Savings for Air Conditioning Scenario Comparison

Figure 5 provides the table for the energy savings for each of the scenarios mentioned. The results for the energy savings of the Efficient Cooling scenario for each baseline scenario type show that between 2025 and 2033, an average of 0.000237 GW (2,076,120 kWh) or more is saved per year.

Energy Savings in GWyr	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033
Baseline Vs Efficiency Scenario Low	0.000237	0.000242	0.000248	0.000256	0.000259	0.000266	0.000271	0.000278	0.000285
Baseline Vs IEA Scenario Low	0.000526	0.000538	0.000551	0.000569	0.000576	0.000797	0.000815	0.000834	0.000854
Baseline Vs Efficiency Scenario Mid	0.000251	0.000258	0.000267	0.000278	0.000283	0.000293	0.000301	0.00031	0.00032
Baseline Vs IEA Scenario Mid	0.000557	0.000574	0.000593	0.000617	0.00063	0.000877	0.000903	0.000931	0.000959
Baseline Vs Efficiency Scenario High	0.00026	0.00027	0.000279	0.000292	0.0003	0.00031	0.00032	0.000332	0.000343
Baseline Vs IEA Scenario High	0.000576	0.000599	0.00062	0.000649	0.000666	0.00093	0.000962	0.000995	0.001029

Figure 5 Energy Savings for each Scenario

The results also show that the IEA Scenario saves more energy for each baseline scenario type than the Efficient Cooling Scenario, with average annual savings of 0.000526 GW (4,607,760 kWh) or more between 2025 and 2029, and 0.000797 GW (6,981,720 kWh) or more between 2030 and 2033.

DISCUSSION

Percentage of households with air conditioners:

Due to a lack of more recent data, the percentage of Surinamese households with installed and functional air conditioning systems is estimated in this report. The simulation used relatively low percentage growth rates to avoid overestimating the results. It's possible that a larger proportion of Surinamese households actually have air conditioning systems installed, which would increase the final energy demand for each scenario simulated for this analysis. This however implies that in the event that the percentage growth rate was overestimated, the simulated energy savings in this report may serve as minimum values. To obtain more accurate results, detailed studies on the percentage of households with air conditioners in Suriname's ten districts would be required to assess each district's contribution to the energy demand.

COP of air conditioners in Suriname's households:

At the time of writing this report, no studies on the COP of air conditioners in various types of dwellings were found. As a result, an estimated COP of 3.52 was used for the average household air-conditioning system based on an Inter-American Development Bank (IDB)-funded energy efficiency audit project in 2022 that gathered specific data and information for a Canadian company called Econoler [6]. During this project, the auditors (including myself) were tasked with visiting various residential, commercial, and industrial customers across the EPAR network (Suriname's largest electrical network comprised of multiple districts) to collect the necessary information and assess which energy efficiency and renewable energy measures can be implemented to improve the energy usage of the aforementioned customers. The most common air conditioner found in residential buildings was the 12000 BTU air conditioner, which had an average COP of 3.0 to 4.0; however, the number of residential buildings audited represents a small percentage of all households. Thus, detailed studies on the COP of air conditioners in various types of dwellings are required in order to obtain more accurate results.

Specific cooling requirements for air conditioners:

The annual average household energy consumption is required to determine the specific cooling requirements for air-conditioning systems in Suriname's average households. Data on average household energy consumption from 2019 to 2023 is available, but estimates for average household energy consumption from 2024 to 2033 are needed. The average household energy consumption in future years was calculated using a simulation in the Low Emission Analysis Platform (LEAP) software. The LEAP simulation did not account for any sudden economic boom that could result from Suriname's discovery of multiple offshore oil deposits in 2020, with oil production expected to begin no earlier than 2028 [7]. These offshore oil deposits could result in positive long-term growth and fiscal prospects for Suriname, potentially leading to an increase in the average household energy consumption.

Penetration of energy forms:

This report only considered electricity-powered air conditioners because they are the most commonly sold in the country. At the time of writing this report, no research had been found on the analysis of different types of air-conditioning systems used in the residential sector in Suriname. As a result, it was assumed that 100% of Suriname's households with air-conditioning systems use electric air conditioners. The Kensho unit, for example, is an air conditioning system that operates without the use of electricity and cools the air with liquid nitrogen [8]. Further research could be conducted to analyse the decrease in energy demand for air conditioning in the residential sector by replacing electricity-based air conditioners with air conditioning systems that do not require electricity.

CONCLUSION

The results of the Efficient Cooling Scenario show that, even if more efficient air conditioners (COP 4.0) are introduced in 2025 and energy is saved, the final energy demand for air conditioning systems eventually returns to its original energy demand. This is due to an increase in average household energy consumption and the number of households with air conditioning. The IEA Scenario, on the other hand, shows that replacing existing air conditioners with high-efficiency air conditioners every five years (COP 4.8 in 2025 and COP 5.5 in 2030) results in greater annual savings. It also prevents the energy demand for air conditioners from returning to its original energy demand, however in this scenario, the existing air conditioners must be replaced every five years with more efficient air conditioners. Given Suriname's economic situation, it is unclear whether this scenario will be financially feasible for residential customers unless the government implements policies to assist residents in replacing their air conditioners.

REFERENCES

- A. Lachman, D. (2018). Re-Energizing Suriname with Less Energy. *Journal of Environmental Science and Public Health*, 02(02). doi: <https://doi.org/10.26502/jesph.96120032>. [1]
- Rapid Assessment Gap Analysis Suriname. (n.d.). Available at: https://www.seforall.org/sites/default/files/l/2015/05/Suriname_RAGA.pdf [Accessed 29 Jan. 2024]. [2]
- Algemeen Bureau voor de Statistiek in Suriname. (n.d.). *Milieu - en Klimaatstatistieken*. [online] Available at: <https://statistics-suriname.org/milieustatistieken-4/> [Accessed 29 Jan. 2024]. [3]
- www.open.edu. (n.d.). *OLCreate: PUB_6172_1.0 Energy Demand Projections with MAED (Model for Analysis of Energy Demand)*. [online] Available at: <https://www.open.edu/openlearncreate/course/view.php?id=9309> [Accessed 29 Jan. 2024]. [4]
- IEA. (n.d.). *Average efficiency of new air conditioners 2000-2020 and in the Net Zero Scenario – Charts – Data & Statistics*. [online] Available at: <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/charts/average-efficiency-of-new-air-conditioners-2000-2020-and-in-the-net-zero-scenario>. [5]
- www.linkedin.com. (n.d.). *Econoler on LinkedIn: #energyefficiency #renewableenergy #project #suriname*. [online] Available at: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/econoler_energyefficiency-renewableenergy-project-activity-7058815596678803456-PXLI [Accessed 29 Jan. 2024]. [6]
- World Bank. (n.d.). *Overview*. [online] Available at: <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/suriname/overview>. [7]
- Jeffay, J. (2022). *No Wires, No Electricity: World's First Nitrogen-Powered Air Con*. [online] NoCamels. Available at: <https://nocamels.com/2022/08/worlds-first-nitrogen-powered-air-con/>. [8]

